

Bioinorganic studies on nickel(II)-zidovudine complex

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Physicochemical and microbial studies on Ni^{II}-zidovudine complex (1 : 1, metal-ligand) have been done in solid and aqueous phase. The metal-ligand interaction has been studied using polarographic method at 25 ± 1° and at ionic strength of 1.0 M (KCl). The complex formation takes place through the nitrogen of the azide group of the ligand. The antibacterial study reveals that the complex is more potent as compared to the ligand.

In continuation of our work on some metal-drug complexes¹, the present paper deals with the studies on the Ni^{II}-zidovudine (3'-azidodeoxythymidine, anti-AIDS drug) complex.

Zidovudine

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behavior of zidovudine and its complex with Ni^{II} : Polarographic behavior of zidovudine with Ni^{II} was found to be reversibly reduced involving two electrons which was evidenced from the plots of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs E . The reduction was found to be diffusion-controlled, which was evidenced by the plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ (h = height of mercury column). The half-wave potential of Ni^{II} ion shifted to more negative value with increasing ligand concentration and the diffusion current shortened, thereby showing complex formation between Ni^{II} and zidovudine. The linear plots of $\Delta E_{1/2}$, i.e. $(E_{1/2})_c - (E_{1/2})_s$ against $\log C_x$ (C_x = concentration of the ligand). The formation of single complex species in solution. Lingane's treatment² of the observed polarographic data reveals 1 : 1 metal : zidovudine complex formation with $\log \beta_1 = 5.29$.

Amperometric determination of zidovudine with Ni^{II} : Ni^{II} gave a well-defined polarographic wave in 1.0 M KCl at pH 6.0 ± 0.1. The diffusion current was found proportional to the concentration of Ni^{II}. The ligand does not produce wave under the said experimental condition. The plateau potential for the polarographic wave of Ni^{II} (-1.2 V) vs Hg pool was applied for carrying out amperometric titration. The amperometric titration of the ligand with Ni^{II} solution revealed L-shaped curves in the current-volume plots. The end-point as located by graphical method, revealed metal-to-ligand ratio of 1 : 1, which corroborates the findings using polarographic method.

IR spectra : A comparison of the IR spectrum shows that the band at 2170 cm⁻¹ due to N₃ (azide group), shifted to 2150 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex. However, the bands at 1750 and 1725 cm⁻¹ remained unaffected in the complex, so also the band at 1680 cm⁻¹ (NH). Hence, the nitrogen atom of the azide group of the ligand is involved in complex formation.

Antimicrobial activity : Antibacterial activity of the compounds (0.01 M conc.) was evaluated by paper-disc method⁴ against *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Diplococcus pneumoniae*. The complex showed enhanced activity against all the test pathogens except for *S. typhi*. The percentage inhibition over control drug are -34, -20 and -12 against *D. pneumoniae*, *V. cholerae* and *E. coli*, respectively. Hence, the complex is found to be more toxic as compared to the control drug against the test bacteria.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of AnalaR grade. Zidovudine (Zidovir) was procured from Sigma. Double-distilled water was used.

Polarographic measurements were made on an Elico 357

DC-polarograph using dropping mercury electrode (DME) as a working electrode, a coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. Experimental sets were prepared by keeping overall nickel (metal ion) and potassium chloride (supporting electrolyte) concentrations fixed at 1.0 mM and 1.0 M, respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 0.0 to 15 mM. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.1 using HCl/NaOH solution.

The amperometric titration was performed on a manually operated setup comprising of a polyflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} A/div.) and an AJCO varnier potentiometer. DME was used as an indicator electrode and calomel electrode served as reference. The capillary characteristics of the DME had $m^{2/3}, t^{1/6} = 2.13 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 50 cm effective height of the mercury column. The pH was measured on an Elico LI-108 pH meter. For amperometric titrations each experimental set having different but known amount of the drug was prepared in appropriate quantity of supporting electrolyte (potassium chloride) at $\text{pH } 6.0 \pm 0.1$ and titrated against the standard solution of Ni^{II} ions whose pH was adjusted to that of the titrate (6.0 ± 0.1).

Synthesis of complex : A mixture of nickel chloride and zidovudine solutions (both prepared in distilled water and

mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio) was refluxed for 1–2 h and the resulting solid complex was dried at 40° and stored over P_4H_{10} .

C, H and N were analysed on a Heraeus-Varlo-Erba 1108 analyser, at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Ni was estimated by the reported method³. All complexes gave satisfactory metal, C, H and N analyses.

IR spectrum (KBr) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 379 spectrophotometer.

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